

Supporting Information

Engendering unprecedented activation of oxygen evolution via rational pinning of Ni oxidation state in prototypical perovskite: Close juxtaposition of synthetic approach and theoretical conception

Rebecca Pittkowsk^a, Spyridon Divanis^b, Mariana Klementova^c, Roman Nebel^a, Shahin Nikman^d, Harry Hoster^d, Sanjeev Mukerjee^e, Jan Rossmeisl^b, and Petr Krtil^{a*}

^a J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Dolejskova 3, Prague 18223, Czech Republic

^b Department of Chemistry, Copenhagen University, Universitetsparken 5, DK-2100 København, Denmark

^c Institute of Physics, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, Na Slovance 2, 182 21 Prague, Czech Republic

^d Department of Chemistry, Lancaster University, Bailrigg, Lancaster, UK

^e Department of Chemistry and Chemical Biology, Northeastern University, 360 Huntington Ave., Boston, MA, USA

* Corresponding author; Email: Petr.Krtil@jh-inst.cas.cz

Figure S1 Rietveld refinement of lanthanum nickel perovskite synthesized without the addition of gelatin assuming a) cubic (Pm-3m, 221) ($R_{wp}=6.65\%$ $R_{exp}=3.27\%$ $\chi^2=4.1357$ GOF=2.0336) and b) rhombohedral (R3c, 167) ($R_{wp}=5.33\%$ $R_{exp}=3.27\%$ $\chi^2=2.6568$ GOF=1.6300) structural model.

Figure S2 Typical full Rietveld refinement of lanthanum nickel oxide samples synthesized in presence of 7.5 g/L of gelatin calcined at 700 °C assuming NiO and La₂O₃ impurities. The figures of merit for the quality of the fit are $R_{wp}=4.78\%$, $R_{exp}=1.87\%$, $\chi^2=6.5339$ GOF=2.5561.

Table S1 Details of the full Rietveld refinement of the diffraction patterns of lanthanum nickel oxide perovskites synthesized with variable amount of gelatin.

	LaNiO ₃	ESD	NiO	ESD	La ₂ O ₃	ESD	
0 g/L	0.998	0.009	0.002	0.007	0	0	R _{wp} =7.85%, R _{exp} =3.29%, χ ² =5.6931 GOF=2.3860
0.3 g/L	0.989	0.003	0.011	0.001	0	0	R _{wp} =6.92% R _{exp} =2.8% χ ² =6.1080 GOF=2.4714
0.8 g/L	0.989	0.001	0.011	0.002	0	0	R _{wp} =7.69%, R _{exp} =2.88%, χ ² =7.1296 GOF=2.6701
1.5 g/L	0.988	0.002	0.012	0.001	0	0	R _{wp} =7.65%, R _{exp} =2.92%, χ ² =6.8637 GOF=2.6199
2.5 g/l	0.977	0.003	0.017	0.003	0.005	0.001	R _{wp} =4.6%, R _{exp} =2.17%, χ ² =4.4936 GOF=2.1198
5.0 g/L	0.945	0.002	0.017	0.002	0.038	0.006	R _{wp} =6.05%, R _{exp} =1.95%, χ ² =9.6259 GOF=3.1026
7.5 g/L	0.949	0.005	0.018	0.001	0.032	0.004	R _{wp} =4.78%, R _{exp} =1.87%, χ ² =6.5339, GOF=2.5561

Figure S3 SEM micrographs of lanthanum nickel oxide perovskite samples synthesized in presence of different gelatin contents.

Figure S4 Statistical analysis of the particle size distribution in lanthanum nickel perovskite oxides synthesized with various gelatin concentrations. At least 400 data points were evaluated for each sample. The corresponding average particle sizes are given in the Figure legend.

Figure S5 current density corresponding to the Ni^{III}/Ni^{II} redox feature as a function of the potential necessary to drive the reaction to a current density of 10 mA/cm².

Figure S6 TEM observations of the lanthanum nickel oxide sample prepared in the presence of gelatin (7.5 g/L) as a structure-directing agent. **a)** low magnification image of sample with selected area electron diffraction (SAED) in the inset, **b)** interpretation of SAED confirming the presence of perovskite structured rhombohedral LaNiO_3 with minor admixtures of NiO and La_2NiO_4 , **c)** HRTEM image of rhombohedral particle showing domains with a 5 nm particle of NiO attached to the surface.

Figure S7 Ni K-edge XANES spectra of the lanthanum nickel oxide samples aged in Nafion containing ink for 4 months. The XANES spectrum of NiO is included as a reference.

Figure S8 k^2 normalized Ni K-edge EXAFS function of the LaNiO_3 sample synthesized without gelatin (\square) and its NLLS fit (red line) assuming LaNiO_3 rhombohedral perovskites structural model.

Figure S9 EXAFS function of the LaNiO_3 samples synthesized with different concentrations of gelatin measured at the Ni K-edge normalized with a) k , b) k^2 , and c) k^3 showing the difference in k -dependence for signal located at 2.8 \AA for the sample synthesized without gelatin in comparison with the samples synthesized in the presence of gelatin.

Table S2 Fraction x of NiOOH – like phase obtained from NLLS fits of the Ni K-edge EXAFS functions of initial powder samples assuming a coexistence of NiOOH like phase with Ni-O distance of 1.91 \AA , and LaNiO_3 phase with Ni-O of 1.93 \AA ($\sigma^2 = 0.004 \text{ \AA}^2$, $S_0^2 = 0.8$, k -range= $3\text{-}12 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$).

Sample (powder)	R	E_0 [eV]	X
1.5 g/L	0.008	8341.8 ± 0.8	0.04 ± 0.11
2.5 g/L	0.0255	8341.2 ± 1.6	0.10 ± 0.08
5.0 g/L	0.0105	8342.2 ± 0.9	0.11 ± 0.12
7.5 g/L	0.0102	8341.1 ± 0.9	0.30 ± 0.11

Figure S10 k^2 normalized Ni K-edge EXAFS functions of the lanthanum nickel samples prepared with different gelatin concentration aged for 4 months in Nafion containing ink. The EXAFS functions are present after phase-correction.

Figure S11 k^2 normalized Ni K edge EXAFS function of the lanthanum nickel sample prepared with 7.5 g/L of gelatin aged for 6 months in a Nafion based ink (\square) and its NLLS fit (red line) assuming a cubic NiO (rock salt) structural model.

Figure S12 XRD pattern of lanthanum nickel oxide prepared in presence of 7.5 g/L of gelatin after 4 month of aging in a Nafion containing ink. The markers for the major co-existing phases ($\text{La}(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$, La_2O_3 , LaO and LaOH , NiO and LaNiO_3) are given in the Figure legend.

Figure S13 Cyclic voltammograms (CVs) of LaNiO_3 catalyst sample synthesized in presence of 7.5 g/L gelatin comparing the initial activity with that after 1 month of aging in an ink containing different binders. The assignment of the binders is given in the Figure legend. Measurements were performed at a 5 mV/s scan rate in 0.1M KOH, working electrode is the catalyst ink drop-cast onto GC-RDE support at 1600 rpm rotation rate

Figure S14 a) CVs of lanthanum nickel oxide samples prepared at high gelatin concentrations after 4 months aging in a Nafion based ink b) CVs of lanthanum nickel oxide samples prepared at low gelatin concentration before and after 4 months of aging in a Nafion based ink. The assignment of the curves is given in the Figure legend.

Figure S15 Typical stability behavior of lanthanum nickel oxide catalysts prepared in presence of gelation after aging in Nafion based ink for 4 months. The presented data were extracted from chronoamperometric experiment on a material prepared at gelatin concentration of 5.0 g/L. The chronoamperometric experiment was performed in 0.1M KOH by stepping the potential from 1.4 V to 2.0 V vs RHE while holding each potential step for 5 min. The potential (black) is accompanied by the ICP-OES based signals of La and Ni (blue and red, respectively) in solution.

